

QUANTITATIVE LIFE CYCLE ANALYSIS FOR FLAX FIBRES

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SUMMARY

Natural fibres are perceived as a sustainable alternative to glass fibres for the reinforcement of polymer matrix composites. This paper reports a Quantitative Life Cycle Analysis for flax fibres (to be judged against glass fibres) using the eight environmental impact classification factors identified in ISO/TR 14047:2003.

Keywords: life cycle analysis, flax, reinforcement

INTRODUCTION

Environmental concerns have resulted in a renewed interest in sustainable composites focusing on bio-based fibres and resins. The fibres most likely to be adopted as reinforcement are bast (stem) cellulose fibres from plants such as flax, hemp, kenaf and jute. However, it is timely to consider whether the claimed benefits of the materials can be justified. The long term aim of this study is to carry out a quantitative and comparative Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of natural fibres compared with glass fibres as reinforcement for polymer composites to establish the most sustainable option.

This paper presents the quantitative Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of flax fibres for reinforcement in polymer matrix composites. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is an environmental assessment method which, according to ISO 14040:2006(E), “considers the entire life cycle of a product from raw material extraction and acquisition, through energy and material production and manufacturing, to use and end-of-life treatment and final disposal”[1]. The outline methodology is defined by the international standards for Environmental Management Systems [1-5]. An LCA study has four phases:

- **The goal and scope definition** – establishing the aim and scope of the study and defining the function or functional unit of the product under examination.
- **Life Cycle Inventory analysis (LCI)** – compilation and quantification of inputs and outputs for a product through its life cycle.
- **Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)** - understanding and evaluating the magnitude and significance of the potential environmental impacts for a product system throughout the life cycle of the product, and

- **Life Cycle Interpretation** – the findings of the LCI or LCIA or both are evaluated in relation to the defined goal and scope in order to reach conclusions and recommendations.

The goal and scope definition

The main objective for carrying out the study is to determine whether the substitution of glass fibres with natural fibres is truly environmentally beneficial. Flax is chosen as the candidate fibre in this study because it is a temperate zone plant and one of the most agro-chemical intensive among the other bast fibres. Therefore the other bast fibres would be “greener” provided the yield/hectare and performance are satisfactory. The product system under investigation includes agricultural operations from preparing the ground to harvest, fibre extraction (retting and decortication), fibre preparation (hackling and carding) and processing (spinning or finishing) operations of flax fibres. For this study, the functional unit is defined as “one tonne of flax fibres ready for reinforcement in polymer matrix composite”.

The scope of the study is cradle-to-gate and the agricultural boundary ideally starts from the farm gate and stops at the factory gate (Figure 1). The production of agricultural products such as fertiliser (N, P and K) and pesticides is included within the system boundary. The agricultural machinery/equipment constructions, production of seed, transportation, storage and man power are not considered within the scope of this study. It was assumed that there is no difference in soil quality and quantity between the beginning and the end of the study. The location, land use and effects of crop rotation are not included in the analysis. The flax long fibre remains as the high value product through the analysis and co-products such as short fibre, shive, dust and coarse plant residues are assumed to have economical value which simply covers their processing costs after separation from the reinforcement fibres. In consequence, disposal costs for these elements are not included.

Figure1. System boundaries for flax sliver and yarn production [6, 7]

METHODOLOGY: LIFE CYCLE INVENTORY ANALYSIS (LCI)

The inventory data for the production of flax fibre has been obtained from the literature, considering various agricultural operations and inputs – fertiliser, pesticides and fibre processing techniques.

Crop Production

Agricultural operations such as ploughing, harrowing, cultivating, applying fertiliser, pesticides and desiccant and harvesting are considered. Three different methods of ploughing (tillage) practices are identified as conventional tillage, conservation tillage and no-till with different energy demands in the production flax fibres (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Energy used in the production flax yarn by different tillage practices [8]

Fibre Processing Operations

Normally, after the crop is harvested, fibre processing is retting followed by scutching/decortication. Scutching is followed by hackling and/or carding which produces sliver. Sliver will be finally spun to produce yarn. Three methods of retting considered in the analysis are warm-water retting, bio-retting and stand/dew retting. The values of energy consumption for retting followed by scutching are shown in Figure 3. In the absence of data specific to flax fibre, bio-retting of hemp and stand/dew retting of baby hemp are considered to have similar energy requirements to flax.

Figure 3. Energy consumption in different retting and subsequent scutching processes [6, 7]

The inventory data for the production of one tonne of flax fibre yarn is summarised in Table 1 from a report [8] based on several original references given therein.

Table 1. Inventory data for the production of flax fibre yarn using no-till practice and warm water retting

INPUTS		
Materials	Value	Units
Seed	497	kg/tonne of yarn
Lime	2445	kg/tonne of yarn
Ammonium nitrate (N)	445	kg/tonne of yarn
Triple superphosphate (P)	238	kg/tonne of yarn
Potassium chloride (K)	368	kg/tonne of yarn
Pesticides	9.4	kg/tonne of yarn
Diesel	9.49	GJ/tonne of yarn
Electricity	35.52	GJ/tonne of yarn
OUTPUTS		
Yarn	1000	kg
Co-products : Short Fibre	4497	kg/tonne of yarn
Shive	7104	kg/tonne of yarn
Dust	2824	kg/tonne of yarn
Coarse plant residue	2304	kg/tonne of yarn
Direct Emissions : CO ₂	9334[9-12]	kg/tonne of yarn
NH ₃	68[9, 13]	kg/tonne of yarn
N ₂ O	14[9, 13]	kg/tonne of yarn
NO _x	6[9]	kg/tonne of yarn
SO ₂	3[9]	kg/tonne of yarn
NO	2[13]	kg/tonne of yarn
NO ₃	0.1[9]	kg/tonne of yarn
NMVOC	0.002[9]	kg/tonne of yarn

RESULTS: LIFE CYCLE IMPACT ASSESSMENT (LCIA)

Eight Environmental Impact Classification Factors (EICF) are listed in ISO/TR 14047:2003 [14] and more coherently defined by Azapagic [15, 16] using different terminology:

- Global Warming Potential (GWP)
- Human Toxicity Potential (HTP)
- Acidification Potential (AP)
- Eutrophication Potential (EP)
- Aquatic Toxicity Potential (ATP)
- Non-Renewable/Abiotic Resource Depletion Potential (NRADP)
- Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP)
- Photochemical Oxidants Creation Potential (POCP)

In the impact assessment interpretation of the LCI data, the inventory data are multiplied by the appropriate characterisation factor to calculate the environmental impact potential, E_x , for each factor, x [15, 16].

$$E_x = \sum_{j=1}^n ec_{1,jx} B_{jx} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

B_{jx} = burden (release of emission j or consumption of resource j per functional unit), and ec_{1j} = characterisation factor for emission j

The characterisation factors represent the potential of a single emission or resource consumption to contribute to the respective impact category [3]. Acidification, eutrophication, global warming and human toxicity potentials are calculated using Eq. (1).

Environmental impact potentials are calculated for the production of one tonne of flax silver and one tonne of yarn in 4 scenarios considering possible tillage and retting options available.

- (1) No-till with warm water retting
- (2) Conservation tillage with stand/dew retting
- (3) Conventional tillage with bio-retting
- (4) No-till with bio retting

The Tables 2 and 3 show the results of Life Cycle Impact Assessment in the production of flax yarn and sliver respectively.

Table 2. Results of the LCIA for the production of one tonne of flax fibre yarn

Scenario	GWP	AP	EP	HTP	POCP	ODP	ATP*
No-till & water retting	15873	146	123	22	0.000012	0.000008	1067
Conservation & dew retting	22586	276	203	35	0.000026	0.000018	2067
Conventional & bio-retting	26576	129	90	20	0.000013	0.000009	941
No-till & bio-retting	26557	129	90	20	0.000010	0.000007	942

Table 3. Results of the LCIA for the production of one tonne of flax fibre sliver

Scenario	GWP	AP	EP	HTP	POCP	ODP	ATP*
No-till & water retting	11062	141	102	22	0.000011	0.000008	1027
Conservation & dew retting	17889	265	195	34	0.000025	0.000018	1986
Conventional & bio-retting	18570	121	89	15	0.000012	0.000009	905
No-till & bio-retting	18549	121	99	15	0.000010	0.000007	905

Units given in above tables are kg/tonne of yarn

* Unit used in ATP is $\text{m}^3 \times 10^{12}$ per tonne of yarn, “Aquatic Toxicity estimations in LCA are notoriously unreliable and difficult” [17]

Non-renewable/abiotic resource depletion potential is calculated using Eq. (2).

$$NRADP = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{B_j}{ec_{1,j}} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

B_j = burden (consumption of resource j per functional unit) and, $ec_{1,j}$ = estimated total world reserves of resource j .

Non-Renewable/Abiotic Resource Depletion Potential (NRADP) was calculated for diesel and electricity usage at each stage of production of flax fibres. Electricity is used for the fibre processing operations (scutching, hackling and spinning). The electricity generation in UK is from 33% of coal 150g/kWh, 40% of natural gas 0.09m³/kWh, 1% of oil 86g/kWh, 19% of nuclear, and 7% of other resources [11, 18] . The NRADP contributions for producing flax fibre yarn and sliver in above 4 scenarios are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Results of the NRADP contribution for the production of one tonne of flax fibre sliver and yarn (multiplied by 10¹⁵)

Scenario	Production	Oil	Coal	Gas
No-till & water retting	Yarn	1200	5.6	3.3×10 ⁶
	Sliver	1100	1.8	1.0×10 ⁶
Conservation & dew retting	Yarn	2600	6.2	3.6×10 ⁶
	Sliver	2500	2.3	1.3×10 ⁶
Conventional & bio-retting	Yarn	1500	17	9.9×10 ⁶
	Sliver	1400	13	7.3×10 ⁶
No-till & bio-retting	Yarn	1200	17	9.9×10 ⁶
	Sliver	1100	13	7.3×10 ⁶

LIFE CYCLE INTERPRETATION

Minimal or shallower ploughing reduces the energy input considerably and especially on a sloping field it reduces the soil erosion or run off of soil sediments. Traditional or conventional tillage methods of mouldboard ploughing drastically affect the soil structure, breaking up its natural aggregates and burying the residues of the previous crop. Therefore the bare soil becomes unprotected and exposed to the action of wind and rain [19]. Chisel ploughing uses ~40% less energy than mouldboard ploughing where drilling combined with a no till pass uses only 6% of the energy required for mouldboard ploughing.

Herbicides applied as desiccant in stand/dew retting have contributed almost 36% of the total energy consumption at this stage. Bio-retting is the most energy intensive method of retting which also includes post-harvest field operations, scutching, rinsing, drying and mechanical softening to produce long fibres. Warm water retting is the process

requiring the least energy but also generates a considerable amount of waste water (~94% of water used).

Co-products such as short fibre and shives are produced from the scutching and hackling processes. These can be used as animal bedding or in paper production. Dust is also produced from processes such as scutching and hackling. The dust can be collected and consolidated as biomass fuel. The long fibre remains the high value product. The mass reductions (as a % green stems) at each stage of the production of flax fibre yarn using 3 different retting methods are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Remaining mass (as % of green stems) at each stage of the production of flax fibre yarn using different retting methods [6, 7]

Total energy used to produce one tonne of sliver is 59.3GJ and one tonne of yarn is 85.4GJ when no-till and water retting is used. Using traditional conventional method (mouldboard ploughing) and bio retting the values are 199GJ/tonne of sliver and 231GJ/tonne of yarn [8]. Published values [20] for glass fibre reinforcements are 25.8GJ/tonne for continuous fibre, which is equivalent to yarn and 54.7GJ/tonne for mat, which is equivalent to sliver. Based on energy analysis, sliver from the low energy route has an embodied energy directly comparable to that for glass fibre mat.

In the production of flax yarn, no-till and water retting has lower environmental impact potentials in global warming and eutrophication than other scenarios. Conservation tillage methods with dew retting has a lower global warming potential than conventional tillage with bio retting and no-till with bio-retting while having the highest impact potentials for all other categories. This is due to using herbicides as a dessicant in stand/dew retting process. Global warming potential is higher when the bio-retting is used but all the other impact potentials are slightly improved. The remaining mass after spinning process is 5.1% of green flax stems when bio-retting is used while 3.9% and 2.3% for water retting and dew retting respectively as shown in Figure 4.

In the production of sliver, the above differences in the four scenarios are consistent to the production of flax yarn with improved set of impact potentials for all categories due to the elimination of the spinning operation. The values from Table 2 and 3 are

normalised and presented as radar plots in Figure 5 and 6 for the flax yarn and sliver production respectively.

Figure 5. Representation of LCIA for production of flax yarn

Figure 6. Representation of LCIA for production of flax sliver

The NRADP is not included in the above radar plots and using sliver as reinforcement reduces the NRADP potentials significantly in all four scenarios due to the absence of spinning operation. No-till and water retting process is the best option in terms of reduced NRADP potential followed by no-till and bio-retting.

CONCLUSION

The quantitative Life Cycle Assessment is carried out for the production of flax fibre yarn using published data and calculations where necessary within the scope of cradle-to-gate. Flax fibre produced by no till and warm water retting has an embodied energy of 59 GJ/tonne of sliver (*vs* 55 GJ/tonne for glass mat). The spinning process raises the embodied energy for yarn to 86 GJ/tonne (*vs* 26 GJ/tonne for continuous glass fibre). Flax sliver as a reinforcement is comparable in energy terms to glass fibre mat. For the other EICF, it has not been possible to identify appropriate data for glass fibres on which to base a comparison. Continuous glass fibre reinforcement appears to be superior from an environmental energy viewpoint to spun flax yarn.

In consequence, the validity of the “green” case for substitution of glass fibres by natural fibres is dependent on the chosen reinforcement form and associated processes. No-till method with water retting is identified as the most environmental friendly option for seven out of eight impact classification factors. Human toxicity potential associated with no-till and water retting is slightly higher than when bio-retting is used. To improve the case for natural fibres, the principal recommendation is for the use of organic fertiliser, biological control of pests and conservation agriculture.

A key consideration for reducing energy consumption and impact potentials associated would be to produce aligned fibre reinforcement without the need for the energy intensive spinning operation. Alternative bast fibres which are less agro-chemical intensive may justifiably be claimed to have lower environmental burden provided they have equivalent yields of fibre/hectare and similar properties (or performance for the full component life cycle). While spinning will permit the use of textile/continuous yarn processes, it will not significantly change fibre orientation distribution factor relative to aligned sliver. The high energy consumption in spinning will need to be balanced against any performance/manufacturing gains from the process.

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